

PREDICTION OF DEATHS FROM COVID-19 IN NIGERIA USING VARIOUS MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS

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ABSTRACT

Machine learning techniques are deployed to process large datasets and can be used for predicting epidemiological events. In this study, machine learning models were used to analyse datasets from the Nigeria Center for Disease Control (NCDC) to explain the effect of total cases and other variables on total deaths from February 29, 2020 to July 20, 2020. Simple Linear Regression Model correctly predicted total deaths from total cases with a R² value of 1 and it showed that the variable considered were significant. It was able to predict that if the total covid-19 cases were raised to 40,000, the predicted total number of deaths will be 924. The Multiple Linear Regression showed a good prediction with an R² value of 0.99 and a RMSE of 0.136. The performance of the neural network model was evaluated using MAE and MSE, which indicated 0.0264 and 0.0013 respectively. Although the predicted total death toll in Nigeria did not manifest, the findings of this study indicate that total death is dependent on total cases. This study reveals the critical importance of prevention of the spread of this disease by all measures possible. This may be achieved by deploying relevant non-pharmaceutical interventions.

Keywords: Algorithm, Covid-19, Machine Learning, Neural Network, Prediction

INTRODUCTION

SARS-CoV-2, a human beta-coronavirus first discovered in the Hubei Province of China late 2019 is responsible for Covid-19 outbreak that was declared a global pandemic by World Health Organization (WHO) on March 11, 2020 (Cucinotta and Vanelli, 2020). Coronaviruses are roughly spherical non-segmented capped particles, with positive-sense single stranded linear RNA (Ribonucleic acid), encapsidated in a nucleocapsid. The viral genome (~31kb) is the largest of known RNA viruses and it is polycistronic generating a nested set of sub-genomic RNAs with 5'-3' sequences that code for essential viral proteins. This family of viruses are characterized by widely-spaced homotrimers called spikes (12-24 nm long) that mediate fusion with host cell membranes after processing by host cell proteases (Brown *et al.*, 2016; Vijgen *et al.*, 2005).

Africa was predicted to be the next population to be hit by the pandemic after America and Western Europe. These predictions were based on the fact that the continent had poor infrastructure and lack adequate health policies as well as facilities. Most of these predictions did not materialize as infection rate and fatalities have remained low. Infection rate according to the World Health Organization (WHO) is less than 5% of reported cases and fatalities are less than 1% despite the population of the continent being approximately 17% of global population. The United States that is less than 4% of global population has recorded about 25% of Covid-19 deaths (WHO, 2020).

According to the United States Library of Congress, Nigeria represents about 20% of total population in sub-saharan Africa. The high rate of human interactions due to socio-economic status and lack of adequate health facilities and policies pitched Nigeria as a possible hub for SARs-Cov-2 infection.

Since the first case in February 29, 2020 in the nation's economic capital, Lagos, the total number of reported cases as at July 20, 2020 was 37, 225 with total fatalities standing at 801 as reported by the Nigerian Centre for Disease Control (NCDC). Following the observed low fatality in contrast to previous predictions, it is necessary to ascertain how the variables; total cases, total discharged, new cases, daily discharged, new deaths, total cases per million, new cases per million, total deaths per million, daily discharged, new deaths per million, aged 65 older, aged 70 older and stringency index, correlate with the observed death rate.

In recent years, Machine Learning Algorithms (MLA) have been used to analyse epidemiological data. Dhamodharavadhani *et al.* (2020) used this approach to build a standard covid-19 model for mortality prediction in India. The same algorithms were used to fit and assess the mortality models and to detect their weaknesses. Some of these predictions did not materialize as the infection rate and fatalities have remained low

Artificial Neural Networks (ANNs) have been used frequently to capture the uncertainty in the time series dataset as they have been proven to be a powerful technique for handling non-linear data (Hong and Zhou, 2012).

Due to the predicted high mortality, the variables; total cases and total death have been of interest to many researchers. Abdulmajeed *et al.* (2020) published an online forecasting model which is an application of ensemble forecasting algorithm in a data constrained environment. This framework automatically mines web data in real-time from reliable sources. Their objective was to establish the lower and upper boundaries of the possible COVID-19 cases in Nigeria using limited data. The study period was February 27, 2020, to April 5, 2020, and data were mined every 24 hours from the NCDC database using a python script.

In this study, we conducted statistical analysis on NCDC data from February 29th to July 20, 2020 to explain the interrelationships between the variables and their effect on total death. This is important as a second wave of infection surges in America and Western Europe.

METHODS

The dataset were obtained from NCDC website (NCDC, 2020) from February 29, 2020 to July 30, 2020 (two hundred and two days). The total number of reported cases as at July 30, 2020 was 37, 225 and the data collected comprised thirteen variables, including; total cases, new cases, total discharged, daily discharged, total deaths, new deaths, total cases, total discharged, new cases, daily discharged, new deaths, total cases per million, new cases per million, total deaths per million, daily discharged, new deaths per million, aged 65 older, aged 70 older and stringency index.

The original data set was used for descriptive statistics and pair plots were created for visualization. The data was prepared and outliers removed. The new dataset had 37, 225 cases and 7 attributes, namely; total cases, total discharged, new cases, daily discharged, new deaths, aged 65 older and aged 70 older. Input variables used for the MLA were; total cases, total discharged, new cases, daily discharged, new deaths. More information about the population of Nigeria as retrieved from Nigeria Center for Disease Control (NCDC) website is presented in Table 1.

The Artificial Neural Network for multiple models was heuristically developed to try and find the best fit model. The model was built using the keras library in Python with one hidden layer. The number of layer nodes in the input and hidden layer were set to 100 each. Adam optimiser with a learning rate of

0.01 was used for building the model. Twenty percent (20%) of the dataset was used for validation and a batch size of 10 was set. Early stopping was also employed to prevent overfitting

Table 1: Nigerian Population in numbers (<https://ourworldindata.org/coronavirus>)

Population	Density	Median age	Aged 65 older	Aged 70 older
206139587	209.588	18.1	2.751	1.447

Python programming language was employed for the predictive task. Pair plots were created for all variables using the seaborn package and multiple linear regression was done.

Ordinary Least Square (OLS) was used to eliminate non-significant features for regression and multiple linear regression model was developed. Simple linear regression model for highly correlated variables was also carried out. The linear regression model of python was fitted using sklearn library. This was achieved using a train: test split of 80:20. The line was fitted for significant variables and the test dataset was used for verification. Artificial Neural Networks (Deep Learning Model) using Keras Library in Python was also developed for predicting number of deaths per million using related variables.

RESULTS

Exploratory data analysis for the data under study is presented in Figures 1 and 2. Some descriptive statistics are presented in Table 2. Total deaths per million during the period of the study was 3.774.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

	New Cases	Daily Discharged	New deaths	New cases per million	New deaths per million	Stringency index
mean	181.41	75.33	3.92	0.87	0.02	49.00
std	235.41	117.76	5.44	1.14	0.03	34.98
min	0	0	0	0	0	0
max	790.00	649.00	31.00	3.83	0.15	85.65

Table 2 showed that the mean for new deaths (3.92) was very minimal as compared to that of new cases (181.41). Also, mean of daily discharged (75.33) was almost half of the new cases (181.41).

Figure1: Plot of new cases in Nigeria

Ordinary Least Square Analysis revealed that Total Discharged, Daily Discharged, stringency index had a non-significant effect on the prediction of total deaths. However, total cases, new cases, new deaths, total cases per million, new cases per million, total deaths per million and new deaths per million were very significant. OLS values that were significant are shown in Table 3. The Adjusted R Squared Value was found to be 1.000.

Figure 2: Pair plot of variables under study

	Coefficient	Standard Error	P Value
Intercept	0.0062	0.013	0.625
Total cases	0.0217	5.86e-05	0.000
New cases	-0.0327	0.004	0.000
New deaths	0.8720	0.069	0.000
Total cases per million	-4.4808	0.012	0.000
New cases per million	6.6988	0.826	0.000
Total deaths per million	206.2388	0.135	0.000
New deaths per million	-179.6883	14.238	0.000

Table 3: OLS Results for all dependent significant variables

For Simple Linear Regression, total cases were used as independent variable (x) to build a linear model for the dependent variable (y), total deaths. The model derived can be written as $Y = 11.319 + 0.023121X$ (Figure 3)

This implies that total deaths will be 924 if the number of total cases were raised to 40,000.

Figure 3: Simple Linear Regression of total deaths on the total number of cases

Multiple linear regression model fitting and subsequent testing on the test dataset revealed a test root mean square error (RMSE) of 0.136 and test set R squared value of 0.999.

Neural Networks

The validation Mean Absolute Error (MAE) was 0.0264 and Mean Squared Error (MSE) was 0.0013. The training was completed in 18 epochs (Figures 4 and 5)

Figure 4: Mean Squared Error (MSE) of Validation data

Figure 5: Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of Validation data

For the test dataset the MAE was 0.0769, MSE was 0.0077. Testing set Mean Absolute Error was found to be 0.08.

DISCUSSION

The number of COVID-19 cases in Nigeria increased since the first reported case on February 29, 2020. A plot of the new cases in Nigeria within the study period peaked at 790 cases on June 28, 2020. Although the new cases seemed to increase over the period, the increase was non-linear. This suggests that with the gradual passage of time, the number of new cases could experience a decline and if there is a new surge, this may be a positive indicator. Pair plots revealed that many variables were linearly correlated. It demonstrates the linear relationship of multiple variables present within our dataset. For this, linear regression was used to determine the slope and the intercept.

Our results indicate that the number of new cases varied from an initial 0 to a peak of 790 new cases in a day, which translates to 0 – 3.8 new cases per million. Total death peaked at 31 deaths per day.

The study revealed that new cases (-0.0327) and total cases/million (-4.4808) were found to have negative regression coefficient and highly significant. The negative regression coefficient may be due to decline of new cases. However, they are significant variables in predicting total deaths. In the same vein, the other variables had positive regression coefficient and were also significant in predicting deaths. The regression model was able to predict that if the total covid-19 cases in Nigeria were raised to 40,000, the predicted total number of deaths will be 924.

Ghosal *et al.* (2020) also used Linear Regression Analysis and predicted the number of deaths in India due to SARS-CoV-2 Regression Models and predicted average week 5 death count to be 211 with a 95% CI. This methodology was also used to predict new cases as well as deaths by Argawu (2020) in Ethiopia with reasonable accuracy. Dhamodharavaravadhani *et al.* (2020) also suggested the use of Statistical Neural Network Models for prediction COVID-19 Mortality Rate in India. Melik-Huseynov *et al.* (2020) created two regression models; one model was based on the increase in new cases and the regression coefficient was 0.02. In the second model, increase in new cases and the number of severe cases were considered; the regression coefficients were 0.017 and 0.01 respectively which varies a little from our results. Contrary to our techniques, Iwendi *et al.* (2020) used fine-tuned Random Forest model boosted by the AdaBoost algorithm model with an accuracy of 94% and a F1 Score of 0.86 for the predictions.

The result obtained from Multiple Linear Regression ($R^2 = 0.99$) showed that, it is a good model for predicting covid-19 total deaths. Also, the RMSE (0.136) for the test data is minimal, indicating that MLR can accurately predict total deaths. Suganya *et al.* (2020) R^2 score of 0.992 on “Forecasting COVID-19 using Multivariate Linear Regression” corroborated the findings of this study. A study from India used a linear regression analysis to predict the average week 5 and 6 death counts. In a study from India, a significant correlation between death counts with total cases, active cases was found which agrees with our study as well. Sharma and Nigam used OLS for forecasting of COVID-19 Growth Curve in India.

Neural network model showed a good prediction for total deaths with a validation MAE (0.0264) and MSE (0.0013). The MAE of the test dataset was found to be 0.08 using 18 epochs. This could imply that, neural networks are vital in predicting of covid-19 deaths. Mollalo et al. (2020) findings on “Artificial Neural Network Modelling of Novel Coronavirus (COVID-19) Incidence Rates across the Continental United States “ were consistent with the study were the Root-Mean Square Error and Mean Absolute Error (MAE) produced minimal error values and hence considered optimal model. Also, Dhamodharavadhani *et al.* (2020) used Neural Network to predict COVID-19 mortality rate in India by considering the error variable. The minimal error values for MSE and MAE indicated the best fit for model.

The study is particularly important since it uses multiple techniques for the prediction of COVID 19 deaths in Nigeria which is one of the most vulnerable countries for viral epidemics.

A reasonably high adjusted R^2 value was found in our study for the predictive models. Furthermore, the validation loss also decreased significantly during training. The test data set results also indicate the model was sufficiently trained without over-fitting and could be used for making futuristic predictions. Also, if the trend line shows an increasing trend, sterner measures can be taken to spread of the virus. All the techniques used in the study showed promising results with non-significant difference between the R squared values

It may also be inferred from our study that no single model can be considered the best model for the death prediction completely and a lot depends on the availability as well as the characteristics of the data.

CONCLUSION

A statistical analysis on NCDC data from February 29th to July 20, 2020 was conducted to explain the interrelationships between the variables and their effect on total death. This was done especially considering the second wave of infection surges in America and Western Europe. Multiple machine learning techniques like artificial neural networks, regressions etc were used for the study. The results

indicate that the variables used in this study are highly correlated with the number of new deaths and this can be used not just to predict new deaths in Nigeria but also to prevent them. If the number of new cases is reduced, the death rate will fall which highlights the importance of non-pharmaceutical interventions like social distancing, masks until a viable vaccine is available.

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